

2023/UNODC/0072

28 August 2023

Dear Mr. Chubenko,

Subject: Invitation to workshop on ‘Monitoring and investigating trafficking in cultural property: Achievements and Challenges’, Lviv, 21 to 22 September 2023

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), Programme Office for Ukraine, presents its compliments to the Scientific-Research Institute of Public Law has the honour to invite you to the National Expert Roundtable Discussion “Monitoring and investigating trafficking in cultural property: Achievements and Challenges” organized with the Lviv National University from 21 to 22 September 2023 in Lviv, Ukraine.

The aim of the workshop is to discuss best practices, achievements, and challenges related to the illicit trafficking of cultural property. Participants will contribute jointly to a summary of outcomes, recommendations, and next steps to combat this crime that will serve to guide future cooperation in this area. The workshop will cover various topics in relation to the illicit trafficking of cultural property including:

1. The international and national legal and regulatory framework and current situation
2. Identification/monitoring of cases
3. Law enforcement responses
4. Financial monitoring and investigation

UNODC will cover all expenses related to travel and participation in the conference in line with UN rules and regulations. In order for us to make timely coordination of logistical arrangements, it would be much appreciated if you could confirm your participation in the event no later than 7 September 2023. The UNODC contact person is Mr. Denys Kadenko, Programme Officer and he may be reached at his e-mail: denys.kadenko@un.org; phone: +380503692052.

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime avails itself this opportunity to renew the assurances of its highest consideration to the Institute of the Scientific-Research Institute of Public Law.

Kind regards,

Harsheth Virk
Head of Office

Mr. Anton Chubenko
Scientific-Research Institute of Public Law

Annex: Draft Agenda